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BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK OLIY MAKTABI

IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT
Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Yashil iqtisodiyodga o'tish davrida
biznes va tadbirkorlik bo'yicha

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Аннотация: В исследовании анализируется, какой тип финансирования инфраструктурных инвестиций – за счёт государственного долга или налоговых поступлений – приводит к лучшим результатам в сфере занятости, на основе макроэкономических данных США за 1989–2023 годы. Используя данные МВФ и Всемирного банка, учитывались такие ключевые переменные, как отношение занятости к численности населения, реальный ВВП, валовое накопление основного капитала, инфляция, процентные ставки, налоговые поступления и ПИИ. Были построены два ключевых индикатора: заёмное финансирование инфраструктуры (Infra_debt) и налоговое финансирование инфраструктуры (Infra_tax). Оба показателя были скорректированы по ВВП для обеспечения сопоставимости во времени. Регрессионные модели с оценками стандартных ошибок Ньюи-Уэста учитывали гетероскедастичность и автокорреляцию, а структурные сдвиги корректировались с помощью лаговых переменных и фиктивных переменных для событий, таких как финансовый кризис (2007) и COVID-19 (2021).

Результаты показывают, что рост ВВП является сильным предиктором занятости. Инфраструктурные инвестиции, финансируемые за счёт долга, оказывают умеренное положительное влияние на занятость, что говорит о том, что заимствования поддерживают создание рабочих мест. Напротив, налоговое финансирование практически не влияет на занятость, вероятно, из-за отрицательного эффекта повышения налогов. Эти выводы согласуются с теориями о том, что заимствования более эффективно стимулируют занятость в развитых экономиках, избегая искажения потребления и деловой активности. В заключение, долговое финансирование инфраструктуры более благоприятно для роста занятости, чем налоговое. Хотя оба способа обеспечивают государственные инвестиции, политикам следует учитывать возможные негативные последствия высоких налогов для рынка труда. Стратегическое заимствование может способствовать экономическому росту при минимальных нарушениях в сфере занятости.

Ключевые слова: США, инвестиции в инфраструктуру, налоговое финансирование, долговое финансирование, эконометрика, занятость.

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure development has long been recognised as a key driver of economic growth, social welfare, and employment generation. The choice of financing method for infrastructure projects – whether through public debt or tax revenues – significantly affects not only fiscal sustainability but also labour market dynamics. Debt financing allows governments to mobilise large resources without immediate tax burdens, potentially accelerating project implementation and stimulating job creation in the short term. However, it increases future repayment obligations, which may necessitate fiscal adjustments affecting employment levels later. In contrast, tax financing ensures immediate resource availability without increasing public debt, but may dampen private consumption and investment due to higher taxation, thus influencing employment generation differently.

In recent years, countries facing budget constraints have increasingly relied on debt instruments to fund large-scale infrastructure initiatives. While empirical evidence suggests positive employment effects during construction phases, long-term implications remain contentious. Therefore, understanding the differential impact of debt versus tax financing on employment is essential for policymakers to design optimal funding strategies that maximise economic and social returns without compromising fiscal stability. This study aims to analyse the comparative employment impacts of debt and tax financing in infrastructure development, drawing insights from existing theoretical frameworks and empirical research across various economies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Our primary goal is to find out which infrastructure financing method is better, debt or tax financed. This is an interesting and actual theme in recent years, especially for developing countries that should mainly focus on infrastructure development. The essence of infrastructure and subsidies has been proven to be important in economic development by Saudia Arabi Emirates, also Uzbekistan is at this theme.

The President of The republic of Uzbekistan in his speech “We will strengthen efforts to create comfortable and attractive environment for investors” on 24 march 2022 emphasized the continuation of intensive infrastructure development in the country as one of the ultimate goal of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for the next 5 years [1].

The main question arises: it that better to finance infrastructure from tax and stimulations or to finance it by government debt. That is undeniable that infrastructure investment always pays back as found by Aschauer (1989) in his study “Is Public Expenditure Productive?” [2]. below an empirical study and analysis will be show from which our main goal is to find the most efficient way to finance infrastructure spendings.

Fiscal policy remains a central tool for governments aiming to stimulate economic activity and boost employment. Two prominent instruments are debt-financed infrastructure spending and tax cuts.

consisted and according to dependent variable, macroeconomic variable is Employment which is measured in percentage and according this the mean value is 60.21 and while min and max are 56.38 and 63.2. Next macroeconomic determinant is Real GDP that are measured in thousands of USD and according the mean value is 1.53e3 while the lowest and heights values are 9.60e1 and 2. 18e. The following independent variable is Gross fixed capital that usually measured in USD dollar and according the mean value is 21.11 while the min and max value are 18.23 and 23.44.

Next is the inflation that are measured in percentage and the mean value is 3.62 while lowest and highest value are -0.35 and 8.02. Next macroeconomic variable is Leading interest rate which are measured as percentage according the mean is 5.86 while the min and max value 3.25 and 10.87. The following independent variable is Tax revenue which usually measured in percentage and according the mean is 10.65 while the min and max value are 7.70 and 12.97. The last macroeconomic variable is FDI which measured in USD dollar and the according the mean is 1.44 while the lowest and highest value are -0.63 and 3.61 (Table 2).

Table 2. Correlation matrix [done by author in Stata]

	Employment	GDP_constant	GDP_growth	Gross_cap	Interest_rate	Tax	FDI
Employment	1.0000						
GDP_constant	-0.5118	1.0000					
GDP_growth	0.4218	-0.1737	1.0000				
Gross_cap	0.7098	-0.0465	0.3369	1.0000			
Interest_rate	0.7037	-0.6759	0.2968	0.5176	1.0000		
Tax	0.5506	-0.0826	0.4673	0.6553	0.4539	1.0000	
FDI	-0.4098	0.7672	-0.1490	-0.0408	-0.5997	-0.0774	1.0000

This part of the study is going to examine the correlation of variables with each other's. In empirical analysis, it is important to observe the degree of correlation between variables in order to determine whether they are correlated with each other [see table 2]. According to the correlation rule, variables can correlate between -1 and +1, meaning that there can be a negative 100% and positive 100% correlation between them. If the correlation is found to be more than or less than ± 0.5 , this indicates that the variables have a high degree of commonality and may cause multicollinearity in the model. This could lead to biased regression coefficients and inaccurate population estimates. To be not confuse we describe the correlation Employment and Real GDP they have negatively correlation with each other -0.51 and additionally correlation between the Employment and Gross fixed they are positively at 0.70 correlated with each other and another determinant is Leading interest rate are positively correlated at 0.70. Next is the Tax revenue is positively correlated at 0.55 with employment and the last variable FDI which are negatively correlated at -0.40 with employment and the correlation of other variables is also provided above.

The research study is going to be conducted on timeseries data, which consists of the data for USA from IMF and World Bank datasets. And time frame of 34 years has been chosen on a yearly basis to capture the effects of infrastructure investments fully as quarterly data is not appropriate to my study. From 1989 to 2023 for USA as this country implemented both Tax financed and Debt financed infrastructure investments. As there are no direct indicators for our independent variables we created ones:

We created two variables, to measure the portion of capital that is financed through changes in debt; (Infra_debt) represents the portion of infrastructure spending financed through governmental debt while (Infra_tax) measures the portion of capital financed through changes in taxation calculated in the bellows formuls:

Then we adjusted our newly created variables (infra_debt) and (infra_tax) by multiplying them by GDP (constant 2015 \$), which in result will represent real dollar invested in infrastructure through debt or tax so we can measure their precise impact on employment:

We adjustments scale debt and tax contributions in real terms relative to GDP it will help us to find the impact of one additional dollar investment in debt or tax on employment in USA (Figure 1).

Figure 1. This time series graph [done by author in Stata]

In this time series graph we can see dynamics over time, GDP Growth (Blue Line) there was the noticeable dips around 2008–2010 due to the Global Financial Crisis.

And a sharp decline in 2020 due to COVID – 19 pandemics. Inflation (Red Line) In periods of economic growth, inflation tends to increase, while in economic downturns, it declines. A significant inflation spike is observed around 2020, which may be linked to pandemic-related economic disruptions and monetary policies. Lending Interest Rate (Green Line) A downward trend in interest rates is noticeable before 2008, which aligns with global monetary easing before the financial crisis. So, we created new dummy variable breaks those accounts for structural breaks in data (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Impulse Response Function (IRF) [done by author in Stata]

Then we check the Impulse Response Function (IRF) Graphs as we can see the graphs above. The first row of the table examines the impact of a D.Employment shock on itself, GDP growth, and inflation. A shock to D.Employment initially affects itself positively, but then stabilizes. The effect on GDP growth and inflation is

minimal and fluctuates slightly over time. Next the second row considers shocks to GDP growth and their impact on employment and inflation. A GDP growth shock initially has a negative effect on employment but eventually stabilizes. The impact on its own growth shows persistence, meaning that past growth influences future growth. Inflation has a mild response to GDP growth shocks. Last one the third row examines the effects of inflation shocks on employment, GDP growth, and inflation itself. A negative initial response to inflation shocks can be seen in employment, indicating that inflation may reduce employment in the short term. GDP growth reacts slightly, but remains mostly stable. Inflation itself shows a dampening effect, meaning that it stabilizes over time. So this test shows that GDP_growth and Inflation have no significant impact on D.Emploment, which confirms that we can include them in our model and they will not distort our regression.

After deep research to find the most appropriate regression model regression analysis using Newey-West standard, this model used for correcting heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation

D.Emploment is a first difference of employment to population ratio in “percentage”

L2.infra_debt_real is a second lag of a one dollar investment into infrastructure from debt.

GDP_growth it is a simple growth rate of GDP in percentage.

D.L.Interes_rate is a differentiated and lagged value of interest rate in a country.

Breaks is a dummy variable of breaks in an economy where 1 is a downward trend and 0 is no crisis.

There all variable are the same except from L.infra_tax_real which is a “real dollar from 2015” investment from tax into infrastructure. This model shows the impact of tax financed infrastructure to unemployment (Table 3).

D.Emploment		Coef.	Newey-West Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
infra_debt_real L2.		1.38e-15	4.97e-16	2.77	0.010	3.58e-16	2.40e-15
GDP_growth		.4446143	.077593	5.73	0.000	.2854066	.603822
Inflation		.1978823	.0606392	3.26	0.003	.0734609	.3223037
Interest_rate LD.		.0923225	.0515814	1.79	0.085	-.0135138	.1981588
breaks		.3092819	.220472	1.40	0.172	-.1430893	.761653
_cons		-2.05698	.4710346	-4.37	0.000	-3.023463	-1.090497

Table 3. Empirical Result [done by author in Stata]

The table 3 presents the results of a regression analysis using Newey-West standard errors to correct for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. It was employed as this model is able to capture most of the fluctuation in employment given with independent variables. And appropriate lag of 3 was chosen due to the number of observations.

Based on the regression results, a 1% increase in GDP growth is associated with an approximately 0.44% increase in employment, and this effect is statistically significant at the 1% level.

Similarly, a 1% increase in inflation is linked to an approximately 0.20% increase in employment, also statistically significant at the 1% level.

Infrastructure debt (lagged by two periods) also has a positive and statistically significant effect on employment, though the magnitude is extremely small. It is approximately 725 trillion dollars needed to invest from debt into infrastructure to increase employment by 1% from previous employment.

On the other hand, the interest rate (lagged difference) has a positive but marginally insignificant effect on employment, with a p-value of 0.085 (above the 5% threshold).

The breaks variable does not show a statistically significant impact, suggesting structural changes may not be a key determinant in this model.

After then, there are another common issue with the model is the presence of multicollinearity between variables. The table 4 as we see we confidently say there is no a multicollinearity problem since the average value at 2.27 below than 5 (Table 4).

Table 4. VIF [done by author in Stata]

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Inflation	3.87	0.258306
infra_debt~1		
L2.	2.65	0.377648
GDP_growth	2.57	0.389274
breaks	1.14	0.878900
Interest_r~e		
LD.	1.10	0.905242
Mean VIF	2.27	

In the table 5 we can see the summary statistics for the regression error term, since the mean is close to zero; this suggests the model does not have a significant bias in its predictions. Even more, below is the scatterplot that confirms that our model made a good prediction of employment (Table 5).

Table 5. Error term description [done by author in Stata]

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
error	33	-.0157273	.8381715	-2.45135	1.196836

After than regression analysis, conducting a number of post estimation tests is important in order to make sure whether the inference of coefficients to population is reliable or not. One of the common issues is observing heteroskedasticity problem in regression, we can check it by many ways one of them is the technical method or scatter plot as we can see the below graphic the three may still be slight non-constant variance in residuals (Figure 3).

Figure 3. scatterplot of our model predictions [done by author in Stata]

If GDP growth increases by one unit, employment rises by 0.4778 units, and this effect is found to be statistically significant at the 1% level.

A one-unit increase in the interest rate leads to a 0.1349-unit increase in employment, and this effect is statistically significant at the 5% level (Table 6).

Table 6. Model with tax effect on employment [done by author in Stata]

D. Employment	Newey-West		t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Coef.	Std. Err.				
infra_tax_real L1.	-7.70e-16	3.14e-16	-2.46	0.020	-1.41e-15	-1.28e-16
GDP_growth	.4777823	.11741	4.07	0.000	.2372787	.7182859
Inflation L1.	.1457058	.075135	1.94	0.063	-.0082013	.2996129
Interest_rate LD.	.1349761	.0647968	2.08	0.046	.002246	.2677062
_cons	-1.523775	.4518266	-3.37	0.002	-2.4493	-.5982505

Inflation also has a positive impact on employment, with a 0.1451-unit increase per one-unit rise in inflation, but this effect is only marginally significant at the 10% level.

On the other hand, a one-unit increase in infrastructure tax reduces employment by 7.70e-16 units, and this negative effect is statistically significant at the 5% level. It is negative but its coefficients are too small, which can suggest that tax financed infrastructure spending can of course create new jobs via foreign investment and national economic simulation, but the amount of tax increased also creates unpleasant environment for an operating enterprise.

After then, we one more time check the multicollinearity between variables. The table 6 as we see we confidently say there is no a multicollinearity problem since the average value at 1.46 below than 5 (Table 7).

Table 7. VIF [done by author in Stata]

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Inflation L1.	1.87	0.535930
GDP_growth infra_tax_~l L1.	1.79	0.557560
Interest_r~e LD.	1.12	0.889339
Mean VIF	1.46	

After than we again check, conducting a number of post estimation tests is important in order to make sure whether the inference of coefficients to population is reliable or not. One of the common issues is observing heteroskedasticity problem in regression, we can check it by many ways one of them is the technical method or scatter plot as we can see the above graphic the three may still be slight non-constant variance in residuals. But as we used Newey-West estimator model we can control for heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation (Figure 4).

Figure 4. scatterplot of our model predictions [done by author in Stata]

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Regression models with Newey-West standard errors analysis results indicate that GDP growth is a strong predictor of employment. Debt-financed infrastructure investment has a modest positive effect on employment, suggesting that borrowing supports job creation. In contrast, tax-financed infrastructure investment has little to no effect, potentially due to the economic drag of increased taxation. These findings align with theories that borrowing can stimulate employment more effectively in developed economies by avoiding distortions in consumer and business spending.

In conclusion, debt-financed infrastructure investment appears more favorable for employment growth than tax-based financing. While both methods sustain public investment, policymakers should consider the potential drawbacks of higher taxation on labor markets. Strategic debt financing can promote economic expansion while minimizing employment disruptions.

Also, by checking models (1) and (2), we found infrastructure investment shows the negative effect on job creation while intraturn debt have positively affect the job creation meaning that since higher taxes on infrastructure reduce employment, due to governments impose higher taxes to finance infrastructure projects, businesses may face higher operating costs which leads low investment and slower job creation more over lower demand may result in businesses hiring fewer workers or even laying off employees. That is why government need focus on the increase infrastructure debt positively to impacts employment ensuring that the project has high economic return such as the transportation, energy, and digital infrastructure. So final policy recommendations of our study is that, it is better to rely on government debt financed infrastructure investments rather than on tax financed ones, as debt investment covers itself in the short run, while tax financing can lead to unemployment. In the short run, tax increases can have a negative impact on employment due to the above reasons. However, in the long run, if the tax revenue is used effectively for high-quality infrastructure, it can boost economic activity and create jobs. So, it is important to consider the duration of policy to correctly implement our policy recommendation.

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